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Abstract

The Flight Dynamics Directorate maintains, in its Aeromechanics Division, fluid dynamic test facilities ranging from a 6 inch pilot water tunnel to a Mach 12-14 Hypersonic wind tunnel. A concentrated effort was begun about 10 years ago to upgrade the diagnostics capability in all the existing test facilities with an emphasis on nonintrusive diagnostics. Also, it was felt that any new facility would be designed with as much optical access as physically and economically possible. This paper describes the efforts made, the results obtained and the plans underway to achieve the goal of providing state-of-the-art diagnostics instrumentation in all the operating facilities.

Introduction

Figure 1 shows a montage of the test facilities in the Flight Dynamics Directorate. The facilities include a 6 inch pilot water tunnel, a 2 foot water tunnel, a 7 foot by 10 foot subsonic tunnel, a 2 foot trisonic closed circuit tunnel, Mach 3 and Mach 6 high Reynolds number blow down facilities and a Mach 12-14 low density tunnel. Each of these facilities has unique test conditions and particular optical access which require specialized optical instrumentation development. In keeping with the goal of maximizing optical access for any new facilities, the design and construction of the two new facilities built during this period, namely the Large Water Tunnel (LWT) and the Subsonic Aerodynamic Research Laboratory (SARL), were directly affected. In the LWT, the design called

for windows on three sides, the complete length and width of the test section. Optical quality glass, 31.75 mm thick, was prohibitively expensive, therefore bubble free plexiglass was obtained and has proven to be adequate for most tests.

Similarly in the SARL with its 2.1 meter by 3.05 meter by 4.57 meter test section, 24 transparent panels, 48 cm by 183 cm were needed to meet the optical access design. Again, optical quality glass was too costly and plexiglass was substituted with the commitment to replace one or two panels with glass at a later date. A test cell was constructed where one of the plexiglass panels was mounted and subjected to the pressure loads expected in the facility. Laser light was then projected through the area where maximum deflection was expected and deflections measured as the pressure was varied. It was calculated that laser beam deflection was negligible and would not affect Laser Velocimeter (LV) measurement accuracy. Laboratory tests, however, show that nonuniform thickness and density can effect measurement accuracy by as much as 0.2%.

In the remaining test facilities, optical access is fixed by the design and limited to small changes, (e.g. the installation of a 35mm fused silica window in the Mach 6 tunnel to allow ultraviolet laser light into the test section) and requires extensive coordination and layers of approval from the tunnel operators. This approval process is further complicated by the desire to introduce seed material, gases other than air and smoke into formerly pristine test facilities. This fact influences both diagnostic design and implementation and makes most of the systems have tunnel specific features or,

at least, requires system adjustments from tunnel to tunnel. Since cost prohibits having dedicated systems for each facility, the current testing and planned development discussed below stress universality of equipment as much as possible.

Measurement Techniques

Diagnostic techniques that are currently in use, under development or in the planning stages include the following:

Schlieren
Scanning Laser Light Sheet
Holographic Interferometry
Laser Velocimetry
Electron Beam
Laser Induced Fluorescence
Chemiluminescence
Optically Smart Surfaces

These techniques will be discussed with respect to the facilities they have been used in, progressing from the LWT to the Mach 12-14 facility in as much as a continuous progression as possible.

Prior to 1980 in FDD, nonintrusive diagnostic techniques consisted mainly of schlieren, shadowgraph and holographic interferometry for off-body flow visualization and oil flow techniques to depict surface streamlines.

The holographic interferograms were made using a pulsed ruby laser and represented some pioneering work by Havener and Radley in 1973.⁽¹⁾ Also in 1973, Wang and Asher used Laser Velocimetry to measure the axial flow velocity in the Mach 12-14.⁽²⁾ Using .3 micron alumina as seed material, velocities of 1524 M/S were measured in the free stream; velocities through a shock wave around a 10 degree cone could not be resolved. This work, done under contract, was not continued.

Since that time, there has been a growing effort to introduce nonintrusive diagnostics into all of the experimental facilities. A survey of the work that has been accomplished and the on-going development will be reviewed by beginning in the low speed LWT and finishing with some development concepts undergoing study.

LWT - The Large Water Tunnel is a gravity fed, vertical facility with a .6m by .6m by 1.2m test section. Continuous flow is possible up to .26 m/s using a closed circuit pumping system. Dye injection through various test models is used to highlight flow structure. By using rodamine dyes excited by laser radiation in the form of a light sheet, the flow details are further enhanced and, with suitable filtering, the laser radiation can be eliminated, reducing excessive flare light. LV was first used in the tunnel in 1988 using natural seed. The velocity distribution measured showed that the centerline velocity was half that of the flow around the edges, indicating a constriction on centerline in the reservoir (Fig 2). The foam flow straightener, suspended just above the test section contraction, was clogged, forcing the water to flow around the edges. The flow was measured again using a fiber optic LV system after cleaning and repositioning the foam and honeycomb structure and rearranging the water recirculation system. The velocity pattern, (Fig 3), was clearly uniform as measured across the test section.

SARL - The Subsonic Aerodynamic Research Laboratory, designed to have 65% visibility (achieving 54% when finally built) became operational in the spring of 91. A sharp leading edge delta wing model was oscillated at rates up to 11 Hz and 40 degree roll angle at angles-of-attack from 15 to 35 degrees and tested up to a flow Mach No. of .52. Smoke and natural condensate (SARL is an open circuit tunnel) were illuminated by a fiber optic transmitted laser light sheet, traversed over the model. High speed video, taped at rates from 250 to 1000 frames/sec with a one microsecond shutter was intensified, digitized and stored for analysis. The complex vortex structure is now in the process of being analyzed.

TGF - The Trisonic Gasdynamics Facility is a closed circuit, variable density, continuous flow wind tunnel capable of operating through a Mach number range of 0.23 to 3.0. The tunnel, with its .6 M test section, has been used for high quality schlieren since its inception. In 1985, LV and laser light sheet capability was added. Most recently,

three-dimensional LV measurements, augmented by laser light sheet flow visualization, were made over a 75 degree delta wing model at Mach 1.9.⁽³⁾ The Mach number was chosen since a computational fluid dynamic (CFD) flow solution to this problem had recently been calculated by Webster and Shang.⁽⁴⁾ Vortex structure was measured at 40 and 80 % chord at angles-of-attack to 35 degrees. This measurement was part of an on-going and developing project for CFD code verification and validation. Qualitative comparisons between experimental data and CFD results show good agreement on defining the region between the primary and secondary vortices. Figure 4 shows a critical problem with LV measurements in vortices, namely seeding the flow to insure adequate light scattering in the core. Maurice⁽⁵⁾ has shown that particle dynamics for flows of this type limit the size of the seed particle to sub-micron size. Figure 5 shows a calculation of various size particles as they travel through and around the vortex structure. Based on these calculations, a particle of .1 microns would be needed to track the vortex to the 40% chord location with a velocity bias of 3%.

These LV measurements and previous ones of Seibert⁽⁶⁾ et al and Maurice and Seibert⁽⁷⁾ in the blowdown Mach 3 and 6 tunnels have led to an extensive effort to calculate the flow tracking of various size silicon oil and methyl alcohol seed particles. Measurements were made over an ogive-cylinder at zero degrees angle-of-attack (AOA) and a sharp leading edge flat plate at two degrees AOA, both at Mach 6, and for methyl alcohol crystals through the shock structure of a 10 degree wedge at Mach 3. Maurice⁽⁸⁾ used a CFD flowfield solution coupled to a particle equation of motion to accurately predict the particle trajectories. (Figures 6,7) This was first done in the Mach 6 and extended to the Mach 3.

As predicted, Laser Light Sheet videos confirmed the lack of seed material in the boundary layer after the expansion corner on the ogive-cylinder. The computations showed that regardless of the size of the silicon oil particles, their momentum was too high to adjust to the expansion. By adjusting particle density in the

equations, the boundary layer could theoretically be seeded with particles one tenth as dense as the silicon oil; the flat plate, however, could be seeded with .2 micron silicon oil. Maurice⁽⁹⁾ has extended this work to the Mach 3 study, which quantifies and corrects particle velocity bias by estimating a particle size using inviscid, oblique shock theory coupled to the particle equation of motion. Particle trajectories and velocity bias are then obtained by using the full Navier-Stokes flowfield solution in place of the inviscid theory.

An attempt to have a combination LV and in-situ particle sizer system developed for flows up to Mach 3 has not yet met with success and the lack of an accurate measure of the particle size during an actual test is still a severe constraint on the LV technique. Monodisperse seeds for universal use are not available or do not remain monodisperse under actual tunnel conditions or are affected by varying seeder configurations.

To improve the holographic interferometry capability in the Mach 3, Mach 6 and TGF, a real time flow visualization system is also under development.⁽¹⁰⁾ This system is a recording holographic subsystem where the physics of the flow is recorded on a glass plate and a reader subsystem reconstructs the hologram, reads the image with digitizing cameras and the image is then bitmapped to a computer for fringe analysis. The fringe analysis is performed using phase-stepped interferometry, the advantage being that the phase can be reconstructed at every point in an image.

In lieu of seeding for LV measurements, exciting the flowing medium itself has been under consideration for many years. Early work, partially sponsored by Wright Labs, looked at sodium injection in nitrogen and iodine injection in air.⁽¹¹⁾ While showing some promise, the inherent non-passive nature of these two elements precluded their use in production type facilities. More recently, Planar Laser Induced Fluorescence (PLIF) or just LIF has looked at the excitation of oxygen in air flows and this technique has shown great promise for measuring velocity, temperature, pressure, density and species

concentration, among others, although not necessarily at the same time nor with the same system. Several different approaches, exciting different regions of the oxygen spectrum are now being tested at various laboratories and universities around the world. Two recent efforts report on PLIF measurements in hypersonic air flowfields and imaging hydrogen flames using LIF.^(12,13) At Wright Labs, under the SBIR program, a system was developed to measure temperature and density at a point along a line resulting from the molecular oxygen B-X electronic transition. The fluorescence radiation is produced by using two laser pulses at resonant frequencies of distinct transition components. These two frequencies are generated by the use of two tunable dye Laser pumped by a single Nd YAG pulsed Laser. As of this writing, the system was to be tested in the Mach 6 wind tunnel in August/September of 91. If successful, some preliminary results will be presented at this conference.

Almost concurrently, development of a chemiluminescence system for use in the Mach 12-14 tunnel was begun. This technique was designed to monitor the radiation from the reaction of $\text{NO} + \text{O} = \text{NO}_2$, the result of seeding the tunnel in the stagnation section with NO and dissociating oxygen in the test section using an excimer laser. This program has been delayed due to technical and contractual problems and will be tested at a later date. Figure 8 shows the proposed measuring schemes.

Currently, an electron beam system provides flow visualization for tests in the Mach 12-14 but is not used as a quantitative tool. Some interesting results of tests of a reaction control model show the interaction of the beam with injected neon and argon gas through a control port as the model is yawed in the flow. Clearly seen on the video tape is the injection plume interaction with the free stream air. Under development for this facility, being developed under an SBIR contract, is an LV system. Seeding the tunnel will be a major concern and much attention is being given to the mechanism that will inject seed into the stagnation region where the temperature is 1350 K. An LV seeder system was recently

tested at NASA Ames in the 3.5 foot which is similar to the design which will be used in the Mach 12. Both liquid and dry seed will be tested.

A new initiative, currently a phase I SBIR, is looking at the concept of using optically smart surfaces as individual or arrayed sensors. Optically smart surfaces are surfaces which have been prepared with specially chosen diffraction properties created by coating or etching the surface with either Binary Optical Elements (BOEs) or Holographic Optical Elements (HOEs). The surface is then interrogated with a beam of light from a transmitter which modulates the light beam, imparting information which is then extracted using a receiver or detector. Possible measurements include gas velocity, temperature, model deflection, pressure, flow properties, skin friction, among others. Figure 9 illustrates possible surface shapes which can be used to create the desired transformation function. The typical dimensions of the required indentations are in the order of the wavelength of light, therefore the surface of the model is virtually unchanged but the impact of these sensors on the boundary layer of the flow must still be examined. Figure 10 shows a model surface treated for an LV Array. This concept is not tunnel specific, therefore it has the potential of working in any environment, including flight. Progress to this point has shown that photodeposition can be used to create the elements on the surfaces; their survival after irradiation by an intense input beam or by abrasion from the flow field must be determined.

Summary

As part of a continuing program to improve the data gathering capabilities in all of the Aeromechanics Division Facilities, a concentrated effort was begun to introduce nonintrusive diagnostics systems into the test facilities wherever possible. The SBIR program has been used extensively to encourage new concept birthing and to provide sophisticated hardware for use when the second phase research is complete. The risk is that the effort may not be completely successful or that the money allocated may not be sufficient to

complete the research as proposed. However, coupled with extensive in-house development, these programs are adding significantly to the testing capabilities of the directorate. As different techniques become perfected, a developing effort to validate CFD codes will become more focused and close cooperation with the computationalists is envisioned.

Acknowledgements

The support of members of the Aero-Optics Instrumentation Group is hereby acknowledged. Mr Mark Maurice, Ms Linda Smith and Mr Charles Tyler for their dedication and commitment to improving the capabilities of the group and their concentrated efforts to educate themselves and Mr Dean Miller for his overall support of test systems, are greatly appreciated.

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Figure 1. Montage of Aeromechanics Division Facilities

Figure 2. LV Measured Flow Field of Large Water Tunnel - Beginning Version

Figure 3. LV Measured Flow Field of Large Water Tunnel - After Corrections

2-D VELOCITY FIELD

$\alpha = 20^\circ \quad x/L = 0.4$

Figure 4. Two-Dimensional Velocity Field at X/L = 40% for Alpha = 20 Degrees (Ref. 3.)

- SCHEMATIC FLOW DIAGRAM:
- 1) SCROLL VORTEX SHEET FORMING THE MAIN VORTEX
 - 2) SECONDARY VORTEX
 - 3) CENTRAL ZONE WITHOUT VORTEX FLOW
 - 4) ZONE INDUCED BY THE MAIN VORTEX
 - 5) ZONE INDUCED BY THE SECONDARY VORTEX
 - 6) ACCUMULATION ZONE (AIR BUBBLE OR COATING)
 - 7) REATTACHMENT LINE

$M = 1.95$
 $Re_L = 4.48 \times 10^6$
 $\alpha = 20^\circ$

Figure 5. Silicon Oil Seeded Flow Field at 40% Chord - Computationally Derived Vortex (Ref. 4)

OGIVE-CYLINDER PARTICLE TRAJECTORIES

Figure 6. Calculated Particle Trajectories Around Ogive-Cylinder at Mach 6 for Various Sized Particles (Ref. 8)

FLAT PLATE PARTICLE TRAJECTORIES

Figure 7. Calculated Particle Trajectories Over a Flat Plate Model at Two Degrees AOA (Ref. 8)

Figure 10. Model With Surface Treated For LV Array

Figure 8. Chemiluminescent Imaging of Mach 12 Flow.

Figure 9. Different Surface Configurations in Binary Optics